

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Pierre****FIRST NAME: Jean Odny****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA - 401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Prof. Cleenewerck****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **When writing papers one of the most important things the writer should avoid is:**

- Paraphrases
- Quotation
- Plagiarism¹**
- None of the above

2. **Ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written on their own words are called:**

- Quotation
- Paraphrases²**

¹ EUCLID University. ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1. Retrieved from <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/> (2015), 8

² Ibid, 23

- Plagiarism
- None of the above

3. **Turabian's Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations offers:**

- A guide on the basis of the research and writing
- A comprehensive insight into the masterpiece on research
- A and B³**
- None of the above

4. **The quality of sources utilized in research activity determines :**

- The success of the study⁴**
- The interpretation of the data
- A and B
- None of the above

5. **Sources are cited to :**

- Give credit
- Assure readers about accuracy of the study
- Show readers the research tradition that informs the work.
- All the above**

³ Turabian, Kate L. 2013. An annual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations: Chicago style for students and researchers. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 2.

⁴ Ibid, 3

6. **To fulfill the requirement of the citation⁵:**

- Researchers need to know the name of the author and the year of the publication of the book
- Researchers need to know which rule of style to use
- Researchers need to know when include a source citation in the paper and what information about the source include⁶**
- None of the above

7. **A dissertation requires:**

- Good planning and understanding
- Time management skill
- Good planning and time management⁷**
- None of the above

8. **The problem statement illustrates:**

- Why the researcher should conduct the study in an appropriate manner
- Why the researchers should enable the reader to understand the topic
- Why the study should be satisfied and enables the reader to understand the central trust⁸**
- None of the above

⁵ Turabian, Kate L. 2013. An annual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations: Chicago style for students and researchers. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

⁶ Ibid, 66

⁷ Ibid, 35

⁸ Ibid, 35

9. **The limitation of the study addresses:**

- The potential weakness of the data analysis
- The potential weakness of the study⁹**
- The potential weakness of the problem statement
- None of the above

10. **According to the European Commission, when mentioning an acronym which is uncommon to the reader, it is important to:**

- State in full for the first time, subsequently followed by the abbreviation¹⁰**
- State in full without mentioning the abbreviation
- Mention the abbreviation without stating it in full
- None of the above

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Blomberg, Linda Dale and Volpe Marie. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from the Beginning to the End*. Thousand Oaks, California: Stage Publication, Inc, 2008.

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⁹ Blomberg, Linda Dale and Volpe Marie. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from the Beginning to the End*. (Thousand Oaks, California: Stage Publication, Inc, 2008), 89.

¹⁰ The European Commission. *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, (2011), 20

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